

Challenging the MEI Neumes Module: Encoding Armenian Neumes

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Abstract

Chant notations are found across a large geographical area encompassing Europe and part of the Middle East (including the Levant and the historical Armenian lands). The Neumes Module represents a collective endeavour on the part of the MEI Community to capture in a machine-readable format the meaning of chant notations. In recent years intensive efforts were devoted towards improving the applicability of the MEI Neumes module, first applied almost exclusively to St Gall notation (also known as ‘East Frankish notation’), and recently extended to include the encoding of Old Hispanic, Aquitanian and square notations (MEI Neumes module, version 4.0).

With this paper, we aim to contribute towards expanding the interoperability of the MEI Neumes module by testing it against the Armenian neumatic notation. From an encoding point of view, Armenian notation shows a higher degree of complexity compared to the neumatic notations so far tackled by MEI. Indeed, unlike all the neumatic notational systems hitherto dealt with by MEI, with the Armenian system we possess no information on either the melodic contour or the number of pitches associated with the neumes. Therefore, one of the fundamental elements of the current Neumes Module cannot be applied to the encoding of Armenian neumes: the ‘neume component’ `<nc>`, that is, a ‘sign representing a single pitched event, although the exact pitch may not be known’. Moreover, encoding Armenian neumes will serve to take even further the recent tendency to encode the visual appearance of the neumes rather than their semantics. In this paper, we outline the challenges of encoding Armenian notations with MEI and propose a solution applicable to future projects aiming at the digital analysis of the Armenian chant repertory.

Introduction

MEI provides a great facility for encoding semantically and structurally rich metadata and music notation (e.g., page layout, notation, and text), including information in visual, analytical, gestural, and logical/semantic domains. As such, MEI has the potential to support the encoding of music repertoires that differ very much from the Common Western Music Notation (CWMN). These include the various musical notations (called ‘neumatic’) that spread across Europe and

beyond the Middle Ages into the early modern era. Neumatic notations were normally employed for writing down plainchant, that is, an unaccompanied monophonic liturgical repertory without rhythmic information in the notation. The long-term goal of the MEI Neumes module is to cover all the surviving neumatic notations but, for the time being, version 4.0 has been shaped and tested merely on a few samples of Western neumatic notations ([MEI Guidelines](#)).

The goal of this paper is to step up the debate on the encoding of early music and to broaden the current Western European focus of the MEI Neumes module to embrace other kinds of early music script. We shall discuss a neumatic notational system that poses new challenges for MEI, over and above the neumatic notations previously tackled in the Neumes Module. Specifically, we aim to enrich the conversation regarding the interoperability and universality of the MEI Neumes module by testing its current version against Armenian neumatic notation. This notation differs in one very important aspect from the notational systems considered hitherto in connection with MEI. Indeed, while those notations convey general information on the melodic contour and the number of notes the neumes represent, in the case of Armenian notation, we are ignorant of both. This is a crucial difference that affects the encoding in many ways, mainly because a fundamental element of the MEI Neumes module cannot be applied to Armenian notation.¹ The element `<nc>` ('sign representing a single pitched event, although the exact pitch may not be known') presupposes that we *do* know the number of pitches represented by the neumes. Therefore, the MEI encoding of Armenian notation requires some brainstorming to circumvent the lack of musical information in the notation and overcome the inadequacy of the current MEI elements and attributes for its description. Nonetheless, it is our conviction that MEI has the potential to become a global project that, in the long run, could embrace all manner of musical repertoires from distant locations and times. The more we test and discuss the applicability and interoperability of the MEI Neumes module, the more this tool will acquire the flexibility to encode "distant" repertoires that may, at first sight, seem to have very little in common.²

In this paper, we discuss the applicability of the current MEI Neumes module (4.0); we then introduce the Armenian notation and the manuscript that we have chosen for the musical examples. Finally, in the third section, we discuss in further detail the challenges of MEI encoding of Armenian notation, and suggest a working hypothesis for future projects entailing the automatic analysis of Armenian chant.

1 Applicability of the MEI Neumes Module

In recent years the MEI Neumes module underwent a series of changes that entailed a shift from encoding based on the symbolic meaning of the neumes towards encoding that also took greater account of the graphical aspects of the notation. These changes eventually resulted in some new elements and hierarchically interconnected attributes (version 4.0).

¹ This problem regarding the potential applicability of MEI to the Armenian neumes was pointed out for the first time in [Utidjian, 2020](#).

² For instance, the Tibetan Yang-Yin graphic notation was employed for writing down chant, and recorded limited information such as rises and falls in intonation (but neither the rhythmic pattern nor the duration of the notes). See <https://www.schoyencollection.com/music-notation/graphic-notation/tibetan-yang-yig-ms-5280-1>.

The MEI Neumes module version 3.0 had been created and shaped for the encoding of St Gall notation (also known as ‘East Frankish notation’, [Rankin, 2018, p. 110](#)). St Gall notation carries a list of Latin names for neumes, each bearing a specific musical meaning, widely acknowledged and accepted in the scholarly literature ([Cardine, 1970](#)). When the MEI Neumes module 3.0 started to be tested against other types of Western European early neumatic notation, it soon became clear that those Latin names—peculiar to the St Gall notation—were neither appropriate nor sufficient to encode other kinds of neume shapes. The first attempt to test the interoperability of the MEI Neumes module 3.0 was made on Old Hispanic notation, which falls within the family of ‘Frankish neumes’ broadly defined ([De Luca, 2020, p. 19](#)). Old Hispanic notation is non-pitch readable and cannot be transcribed into a modern score, as it provides us with only a minimum of musical information.³ This notation (especially as found in earlier sources) stands out for its complexity and richness of graphical detail. When compared to St Gall notation, the Old Hispanic notation greatly expands the number of neumes and music-related signs employed to convey musical information. Applying MEI to Old Hispanic notation prompted new reflections on the need for a terminology for neume description that could at the same time be reliable, unambiguous, and comprehensible for a machine ([De Luca et alii, 2019a](#)). Besides, the limited amount of musical information conveyed to modern readers by the Old Hispanic neumes meant that encoding could not be based exclusively on the semantics of the notation, but should also take into account its graphical features. This new approach to music encoding based on both the visual and the semantic resulted in a brand-new element, the `<nc>`, and in a long list of new attributes that clarify the graphical appearance of the `<nc>`: `@tilt`, `@s-shape`, `@rellen`, `@curve`, `@angled`, etc. ([MEI Guidelines](#)). These changes to the MEI Neumes module were presented at MEC 2019 in Vienna ([De Luca et alii, 2019b](#)); but not much has changed since then in the organization of the newly-defined list of elements, attributes and hierarchy of the MEI Neumes module.

The MEI Neumes module 4.0 was validated against a small sample of Western notations (namely St Gall, Old Hispanic, Aquitanian and square notation), while notations from Eastern Europe and the Middle East were entirely neglected. This is a fundamental *lacuna* in the current applicability of the MEI Neumes module, as there are historical and methodological reasons that justify the study of the surviving neumatic notations from Europe and part of the Middle East as part of a larger phenomenon. Chant notations served the same purpose, namely capturing Christian liturgical monody in written form. The surviving commonalities existing among liturgical chants and notations from this large geographical area suggest that music scribes shared, to some degree, writing techniques and notational signs. Eventually, scribes made their own peculiar selection of musical signs and techniques at a regional—and sometimes local—level; but still, it remains crucial to study neumatic notational systems for their idiosyncrasies while keeping an eye on the bigger picture of the writing and transmission of early music.

Undertaking the automatic analysis of chant manuscripts from such a large geographical area is a dream for any early music scholar, but the current technologies are not yet ready for

³ Modern readers can barely read the number of notes represented by Old Hispanic neumes, and only very basic information on the melodic contour. Indeed, we have no information on the exact width of the melodic intervals, but only a general understanding of the melody according to the values ‘high’, ‘low’, ‘same’, or ‘neutral’ — the latter employed when the musical relationship of a note compared to its predecessor is unclear.

this task. Thus, we must hone our tools: open up the discussion around music encoding to include more notational systems and engage in further discussions between scholars from varied backgrounds. Indeed, testing the MEI Neumes module against new notations could have a profound impact on the encoding. For instance, if we add the Armenian neumes to the list of neumatic signs encoded by MEI, we see that the list suddenly (and greatly) expands.⁴ Furthermore, the complete lack of a modern understanding of the number of notes and the melodic contour associated with Armenian notation means that the encoding of this repertory must rely *exclusively* on the visual appearance of the neumes, rather than on the combination of both the symbolic and visual aspects.

In the following section we provide an overview of Armenian medieval notation (history, sources, and bibliography) and introduce the manuscript that we have selected for the MEI analysis that follows in Section 3 below.

2 Armenian Notation

2.1 *The Armenian medieval neumes*

The Armenian medieval neumes pose a number of tantalising open musicological problems. The earliest Armenian neumes hitherto encountered by Haig Utidjian may be found on folio 294v of the oldest Lectionary in San Lazzaro, Venice, namely V169⁵ (tenth to eleventh centuries) – curiously enough, constituting the sole neumated excerpt in the entire codex. The neumes do not seem to be a later addition.⁶ The neumations in hymn codices continued to be copied from generation to generation, and were reproduced in printed editions until recent decades. Yet we are unable to decipher the notation. The most recent fundamental study of the Armenian neumes is that by the Constantinopolitan church musician and musicologist, Etia Tntesean (1834–1881).⁷ Little has been added to our knowledge of the medieval system since his own contributions (though much dubious material has since been published). Latterly, we have gained insight into the limited use to which the neumes were put in nineteenth-century Constantinople;⁸ but the comparatively crude procedures then applied ought not to be conflated with the manner in which the notation would have been used in medieval times.⁹

⁴ Among the new signs there are some long and complex neumes which seem particularly challenging for encoding purposes. See Section 3, below.

⁵ We follow the sigla officially recommended by the *Association Internationale des Études Arméniennes* throughout the text. V: Mekhitarist Monastery, San Lazzaro, Venice; M: Matenadaran Institute of Ancient Manuscripts, Yerevan.

⁶ However, miscellaneous parchment flyleaves have been used by later binders, some with *erkat'agir* (uncial, and thus deemed archaic) script bearing neumations. These are of uncertain date, and have been used speculatively by Soviet Armenian musicologists and other nationalists thereafter, in an attempt to support the contention that Armenian neumes are of greater antiquity than those of other traditions.

⁷ [Tntesean, 1874, p. 115](#); henceforth, this volume will be referred to in abbreviated transliteration, as *Nkaragir ergoc'*.

⁸ For a succinct treatment, see [Utidjian, 2017, p. 261–284](#). A fuller treatment may be found in [Utidjian, 2018a](#).

⁹ For an up-to-date discussion, see [Utidjian, 2018b, p. 274–330](#).

2.2 An Earlier Digital Project Involving Armenian Neumes

An earlier research effort by Haig Utidjian, implemented by Vladimír Faltus, led to the design of simple glyphs, both for the Armenian medieval neumes (the “VF Neumatic system”, Figure 1 in Section 2.3), reproducing the symbols used in the Jerusalem 1936/Antelias 1997 Portable Hymnal (in turn largely replicating the repertoire of neumes found in the *editio princeps* of Amsterdam 1664-1665), and for the Limōnčean symbols¹⁰ (“VF Aneumatic”), reproducing the symbols in Tntesean’s Hymnal¹¹ (Constantinople, 1934 – believed to use designs by Yovhannēs Miwhēntisean).¹² The latter were extended and further developed at the initiative of Jacob Olley in connection with the University of Münster’s *Corpus Musicae Ottomanicae* (CMO) project, on the basis of some forty codices, resulting in a set of 210 distinct glyphs (culminating in the “VF OttoAneumatic system”).¹³ The CMO researchers favoured Unicode, to ensure that the edition be compatible with widely used digital standards. The transcriptions are converted to xml using a customised schema based on the MEI guidelines. The purpose of the system is to allow scholars to insert symbols into a transcription to reflect the layout and characteristics of the original manuscript sources.

2.3 A Manuscript for Analysis

For the present endeavour, the choice of principal source is a non-trivial matter. Should we confine ourselves to a particular genre, and if so, which? Ought a printed edition be used, or a manuscript? And in either case, which particular source might best suit our purpose and why? Armenian neumated sources are extant in a variety of genres, the chief of which are hymnals, books of odes, and highly specialized manuals of breviary chants (known as *manrusmunk’* – literally “minute study” – including some very intricate notation, exhibiting signs some of which are generally not to be found elsewhere). To these, we may add other types of liturgical volumes that include small numbers of neumated items (some lectionaries and euchologia – books of rituals – fall into this category), and gospels with a very limited repertory of signs (associated with ecphonic chant). Though the system of notation found in these diverse sources probably constitutes a single continuum, this is uncertain, so it would be prudent to confine ourselves *pro tempore* to a single genre. The Armenian Hymnal is a “closed” canon, exhibiting stable neumations and standardized content; though fairly complex chains of neumes occasionally occur, the genre does not exhibit extreme complication; and it is represented by a relative abundance of exemplars (with the monastery of San Lazzaro in Venice alone keeping 139 codices). This bodes well for future comparative work with high-throughput methods.

We considered printed sources – ranging from the *editio princeps* (Amsterdam, 1664-1665) to the standard Jerusalem Portable Hymnal of 1936 (including its more recent reincarnation of

¹⁰ This was a novel, aneumatic notational system that redefined a number of the medieval Armenian neumes in a system similar to tonic sol-fa or the “Lesbian” system due to Georgios Lesbios, and emerged in Constantinople around 1815.

¹¹ For a discussion of this publication see [Utidjian, 2018-2019](#).

¹² For a fuller discussion see [Utidjian, 2022](#).

¹³ These are in the public domain, and may be downloaded from the address https://repository.de.dariah.eu/1.0/dhcrud/21.11113/0000-000E-5CAE-8?fbclid=IwAR2MQ5xZHuavb1JskYjdvAL7pH372iqqIVliz-rzw_OzZP9NsjqLRzqku9E (accessed 22 December, 2021).

Antelias, 1997). Of special interest is the remarkable edition (Venice, 1898) of Archbishop Ignatios Kiwreftan (1833–1920), who alone strove to reproduce all dots, significant letters, and minute variations in angle of inclination. Yet even this typographical feat inevitably entailed reduction as well as redaction. Printed editions would simplify our task, having already resolved ambiguities and simplified complexities, and also rendering optical recognition far easier. But the gain could prove illusory – some raw information embodied in codices would be sacrificed, and potentially arbitrary decisions implicitly made by distant generations of editors could well prove misleading for our future research endeavour, some of which would seek to answer the very questions that may have been swept under the carpet by early editors.

The earliest dated codex is M9838 (Jerusalem, *anno* 1193); but it has been abbreviated – with the omission of words and the abbreviation of such words as have been retained. Another early (but undated – probably twelfth century) codex, V97, is atypical – *inter alia* using the neume *erkar* in lieu of a variety of other “long” neumes. The hymnal of King Het’um II (V29, prob. 1289-1305) is refined, but the scribe slightly idiosyncratic in some of his shapes, and the codex sadly shorn of “catholic” folios (in the process also sacrificing parts of orthodox canons). At length, we arrived at codex V154 (Sis, *anno* 1295, 328 paper folios, 9.5 x 13 cm), which captures much of the complexity of V29 but without some of the idiosyncrasies of its scribe; V154 (unlike V29) is almost intact (and thus very nearly complete), and may be considered one of the oldest examples known to us of a stabilised Cilician tradition, and thus representative of a very large set of codices. It was moreover considered by Fr. Sahak Čemčemean of blessed memory (perhaps the greatest expert of hymnal manuscripts of the twentieth century) to be particularly suitable as a model in respect of its neumations.¹⁴ We have accordingly decided to initiate our work on the basis of Armenian medieval neumes as they appear in V154 (Figure 2).

¹⁴ See [Čemčemean, 1993, col. 37, «խազագրութեան այ կրնայ օրինակ հանդիսանայ ձեռագիրս»](#).

Figure 1: VF Neumatic keyboard, version 1.1.

Figure 2: Folios 64v-65r from the manuscript V154.

3 An MEI Encoding of Armenian Neumes

Contemporary readers are entirely ignorant of the meaning of Armenian notation. Armenian neumes are thus music “for the eye” alone; therefore, encoding must rely exclusively on the visual level, leaving aside any semantic elements (because these are unknown). The palaeographical observation of the neumes in the selected manuscript demonstrated that the neumes were made up of simple graphical components (short and long strokes, loops, zigzags etc.) assembled together in many creative ways to form all the neume shapes found in the manuscript. These neume shapes are also found in other Armenian liturgical books and some of them were also employed in some ‘Frankish’ notations (see, for instance, neume ‘a’ in Table 1).

	ARMENIAN NEUMES	MEI
a		<pre><neume> <gc tilt="se"/> <gc tilt="ne" relen="1"/> </neume></pre>
b		<pre><neume> <gc tilt="ne"/> <gc angled="true"/> <gc angled="true"/> <gc tilt="se"/> <gc tilt="ne" relen="1"/> <gc tilt="ne" hooked="true"/> </neume></pre>
c		<pre><neume> <gc c-shape="w"/> <gc c-shape="e"/> </neume></pre>
d		<pre><neume> <gc tilt="ne"/> <gc tilt="e" curve="c" relen="1"/> <gc tilt="ne" relen="s"/> <gc angled="true"/> <gc angled="true"/> <gc tilt="se"/> </neume></pre>
e		<pre><neume> <gc tilt="ne"/> <gc c-shape="n" relen="1"> <tick tilt="se" place="above" connected="false" quantity="2"/> </gc> </neume></pre>

f		<pre> <neume> <gc tilt="ne" hooked="true"> <tick tilt="se" place="below-right" connected= "true" quantity="1"/> </gc> </neume> <neume> <gc c-shape="s"/> <gc tilt="ne"/> <gc tilt="e"/> </neume> </pre>
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Table 1: MEI encoding of a selection of Armenian neumes.

We envisage that the MEI encoding of Armenian neumes requires the creation of a new element that could represent the basic graphical components (strokes, loops, zigzag shapes, etc.) while circumventing our lack of knowledge of the number of notes represented in the notation. The new `<gc>` ‘graphical component’ would be a child element of `<neume>` and could be defined as: ‘A basic graphical component of undeciphered neumes that is consistently employed in the notation. It is likely that some musical significance was originally associated with it by convention, but that meaning is now lost’. `<gc>` could be applied to the encoding of Armenian notation and to any other neumatic notation that does not convey musical information to modern readers. `<gc>` would have all the same attributes as `<nc>`, which indeed were originally created to capture some graphical features of the neumes in the encoding. But, even if we reuse all the attributes of `<nc>` and apply them to `<gc>`, this would not be sufficient to cover all the basic graphical components of Armenian notation. Thus, we propose the creation of the new attribute `@c-shape` that allows greater versatility in encoding and allows us to capture many more shapes. This attribute would be defined as: ‘The initial direction for a c-shaped pen-stroke; viz, "w" for the standard letter C, "e" for its mirror image, "s" for the letter C turned 90-degrees anti-clockwise, and "n" for its mirror image’. In Table 1, above, we have gathered a representative sample of Armenian neumes from the selected source and provided a MEI encoding according to the elements and attributes of the MEI Neumes module, to which we added the new `<gc>` and `@c-shape`. Further refinements, adjustments, and modifications to the MEI Neumes module were also required, and they are presented in the following explanation (each neume identified below is found in Table 1).

NEUME A: This shape is also found in Old Hispanic, Saint Gall and central Italian notations. In Armenian notation `<nc>` is replaced by `<gc>` but the encoding is otherwise based on the use of the attributes `@tilt` and `@rellen`, providing information on the strokes, their inclination, and their relative length.

NEUME B: The zigzag can be captured in the encoding by means of the existing attribute `@angled`.¹⁵ The direction of the zigzag is given by the direction of the very first pen-stroke, which is encoded with `@tilt`, in this case pointing ‘north-east’. The encoding of this neume requires an adjustment to the current MEI Neumes module. Indeed, the attribute `@hooked` is currently described as: ‘Pen stroke has an extension; specific to Hispanic notation’. We suggest

¹⁵ Zigzag pen-strokes are also found in Old Hispanic notation.

instead that this attribute not be specific to Old Hispanic notation; it could thus be conveniently applied to capture in the encoding the tiny pen-stroke extensions often found in Armenian notation. Hence, the description of `@hooked` would simply be: ‘Pen stroke has an extension’.

NEUME C: Loops are also found in Old Hispanic notation, but are part of the neumatic connection between two neume components. In the case of Armenian notation, the addition of the new attribute `@c-shape` allows us to capture the loop in the encoding, and can also be employed in all situations where curved strokes are used.¹⁶

NEUME D: This neume can be encoded by means of the elements and attributes already described. It can be broken down into six graphical components, namely: a straight pen-stroke pointing ‘north-east’ (tilt); a longer curved pen-stroke initially pointing ‘north’; a short tilt pointing ‘north-east’; two angled pen-strokes (each with a v-shape); and a final pen-stroke pointing ‘south-east’.

NEUME E: The challenge of this neume lies in the encoding of the two short pen-strokes placed above the long curved stroke. Our solution consists in the creation of the new element `<tick>`, described as: ‘A short pen-stroke placed close to the principal part of the neume’.¹⁷ `<tick>` would be a child element of `<gc>` and then described by means of the following attributes:

`@tilt`: ‘The direction towards which the mark points, e.g. north, north-east, etc. {n | ne | e | se | s | sw | w | nw}’

`@place`: ‘Captures the placement of the tick with respect to the graphical component with which it is associated. {above | below | left | right | above-left | above-right | below-left | below-right}’

`@connected`: ‘A graphical connection to the previous nearest graphical component. If there is no graphical connection, a spatial gap separates the tick and the nearest `<gc>`. {true | false}’

`@quantity`: ‘The number of ticks. {1 | 2 | 3 etc.}’

NEUMES F: The encoding of these two neumes requires most of the elements described above. The first neume is particularly useful in exemplifying how `@hooked` and `<tick>` work. Indeed, the final extension of the long pen-stroke is captured in the encoding by the attribute `@hooked`, while the tiny pen-stroke placed underneath the long straight tilt that points north-east would be encoded as a `<tick>`, although in this case it is graphically connected to the nearest `<gc>` and therefore its value is ‘true’.

The second neume is reminiscent of shapes found in other Western European notations, but in this case, we consider it as being constituted from three graphical components: a c-shape and two tilts respectively pointing north-east and east.

Conclusion

MEI is a visionary project that anticipates the future by preparing the tools to face new challenges. We aim at the long-term goal of the automatic analysis of extant neumated corpora, to enable large-scale comparisons across manuscripts, and to deepen our understanding of the intermingling of orality and writing over the centuries, shaping the musical repertory that

¹⁶ We assume that the loop was written starting from the top and then turning the pen anticlockwise.

¹⁷ The existing `<hispanTick>` (‘Hispanic tick’) is a child element of `<nc>` and it is described by the following attributes: `@tilt` and `@place`.

reached us in musical manuscripts. A digital approach to the analysis of notated chants in Armenian notation could enable the exploitation of large amounts of data to reveal potential patterns that would elude ad-hoc, small-scale investigations with the unaided eye. The MEI Neumes module has the potential to serve as an ideal tool for the analysis of Armenian neumes. The flexibility and openness of MEI, together with the fact that scholars with varied expertise (IT specialists, historical musicologists, palaeographers, etc.) contribute to its ongoing development and refinement, promise great advances in this direction. In this paper, we tested the applicability of the MEI Neumes module on thirteenth-century undecipherable Armenian neumes; the lack of musical information required us to base the encoding solely upon the visual data. Our approach to the encoding of Armenian notation entails breaking down the neume shapes into basic graphical elements employed consistently in the notation, either separately or in combination, to form the neume shapes. Thus, we have created some new elements and attributes, and proposed further small adjustments to the MEI Neumes module. We believe that with the small changes described above we could open up new possibilities for early music research, and increase the applicability of MEI to early musical repertoires.

We hope that this reflection on the applicability and, consequently, on the current limits of the MEI Neumes module 4.0 will stimulate scholars to contribute towards the sharpening of our MEI tools required to encode more diverse types of neumes. MEI can grow through the contributions of its community, and we hope that the ideas presented here will serve to encourage and inspire other scholars to contribute with their expertise to hone the MEI Neumes module to accommodate further musical repertoires, thus widening the adoption of MEI for future projects – involving editions, hypertexts, data repositories, and their fruitful analysis.

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